

Effect of Process Variables on Properties of MVS Yarns

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Abstract:

This paper examines the influence of various process variables, including nozzle air pressure, yarn delivery speed, and card cylinder speed, on the characteristics of MVS yarns produced using Murata vortex spinning (Vortex III 870 system). The findings reveal that nozzle air pressure and yarn delivery speed exert significant influence on yarn evenness, imperfections, hairiness, and tensile properties. Raising the nozzle air pressure in vortex spinning has the effect of enhancing yarn tenacity and unevenness in the yarn structure. Conversely, this increase in air pressure tends to reduce the level of hairiness in the resulting spun yarn. Overall, the analysis demonstrates that higher card cylinder speeds tend to enhance properties such as unevenness and hairiness of the yarn.

Keywords: MVS yarn, Process variable, Viscose yarn, Vortex spinning, Yarn properties

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1. Introduction

Meeting the stringent quality standards for knitted fabrics, especially concerning their appearance and comfort, remains a significant challenge. Traditional air-jet spun yarns have limited applicability in knitting due to their adverse impact on fabric hand, finding primary use in woven products like table cloths, bed sheets etc. To address these limitations and cater to the regular wear and casual markets, Murata Machinery Ltd. developed the Vortex III 870 spinning system. This innovative yarn production method, characteristic of vortex-spun yarns, has successfully mitigated several drawbacks associated with air-jet spun yarns, especially for specific end-use applications. The performance of fabrics prepared from vortex-spun yarns is not solely influenced by fabric structure but also by the unique structure and properties of these yarns [1-3].

Various process parameters employed in vortex spinning can induce structural and property changes in vortex-spun yarns, encompassing factors such as fiber alignment categories, spatial configuration within the yarn, fiber packing density of the yarn cross-section, yarn tensile properties, evenness, and hairiness [4-7]. These alterations subsequently impact the characteristics of fabrics manufactured using vortex-spun yarns.

While prior research has primarily focused on comparing the performance of fabrics constructed from different yarn types, including ring-spun, compact-spun, rotor-spun, and vortex-spun yarns [8-11], there has been a notable scarcity of studies exploring the relationship between process parameters and the properties of MVS yarns particularly spun on Vortex III 870 spinning system. Some limited investigations have examined specific aspects, such as the low-stress and thermal comfort characteristics of woven fabrics made from polyester-cotton MVS yarns in relation to twisting jet pressure, delivery speed, and nozzle distance [1]. Similarly, others have delved into the impact of process parameters, such as nozzle pressure, yarn delivery speed, and yarn count, on the properties of viscose knitted fabrics [3].

This dearth of comprehensive literature addressing the intricate interplay between yarn process parameters and fabric characteristics leaves spinners in a state of uncertainty when determining the ideal process parameters for achieving specific fabric characteristics. Consequently, there is a pressing need for research that can aid yarn manufacturers in optimizing MVS process parameters, thereby expanding the potential applications of MVS yarns in the production of knitted garments. The focus of this study revolves around examining the impact of key

process parameters, specifically nozzle air pressure, yarn delivery speed in MVS, and carding machine cylinder speed, on the properties of MVS yarns used in the manufacturing of knitted garments.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Samples

To conduct this study, 100% viscose fibers with a length of 38 mm and a fineness of 1.2D have been used. Yarn samples of 40s Ne were meticulously prepared on Murata vortex spinning (using Vortex III 870 spinning system), in accordance with an experimental plan designed using the Box and Behnken methodology [12]. The specific details of the experimental plan, as well as the actual values of the three variables corresponding to the coded levels, are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Experimental plan for MVS machine variables used for yarn samples

Combination No.	Nozzle pressure MPa (x_1)	Yarn delivery speed m/min (x_2)	Card cylinder speed rpm (x_3)
1.	-1	-1	0
2.	1	-1	0
3.	-1	1	0
4.	1	1	0
5.	-1	0	-1
6.	1	0	-1
7.	-1	0	1
8.	1	0	1
9.	0	-1	-1
10.	0	1	-1
11.	0	-1	1
12.	0	1	1
13.	0	0	0
14.	0	0	0
15.	0	0	0

Table 2: Actual values corresponding to coded levels

Coded level	Actual value		
	Nozzle air pressure MPa (x_1)	Yarn delivery speed m/min (x_2)	Card cylinder speed Rpm (x_3)
-1	0.50	380	440
0	0.52	410	500
1	0.54	440	560

2.2 Test Methods

Prior to testing, all yarn samples underwent a conditioning period lasting 48 hours under standardized test conditions, maintaining a temperature of 27 ± 2 °C and relative humidity at $65 \pm 2\%$.

Yarn tensile properties were assessed using the Uster Tensorapid 4 instrument, with a gauge length of 500 mm, a test speed of 5000 mm/min, and a pre-tension of 0.5cN/tex. The yarn tenacity value was determined as the average of 30 individual tests.

To evaluate yarn evenness and hairiness (H values), we employed the Uster Tester 5-S800, operating at a yarn speed of 800 m/min and a testing duration of 0.5 minutes. The evenness and hairiness values for each yarn sample were computed as the mean of 10 test results.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Statistical Analysis

To derive meaningful insights from our experimental data concerning the properties of various MVS yarns, we employed the SYSTAT 13 computer statistical tool program. This enabled us to formulate response surface

equations that encapsulate the intricate relationships within the data. The response surface equations, along with the squared multiple correlation coefficients of the yarns, are comprehensively presented in Table 3.

In interpreting these equations, it is essential to consider the sign of the coefficients. A negative coefficient in a response surface equation signifies that a particular characteristic decreases as the corresponding variable increases, while a positive coefficient indicates that the characteristic increases with an increase in the variable. It is crucial to recognize that the trend is influenced not only by the sign but also by the magnitude of the coefficients associated with squared and interaction terms. Visual representations of these relationships can be observed in the spatial diagrams (Figs 1-4).

Table 3: Response surface equations for characteristics of yarn

Characteristic	Response surface equation	Squared multiple regression coefficient (R ²)
Tenacity (gf/tex)	$14.210 + 0.484 X_1 - 0.149 X_2 - 0.128 X_1^2 - 0.055 X_3^2 - 0.125 X_1 * X_2$	0.998
Elongation-at-break, %	$6.837 + 0.100 X_2 + 0.614 X_1^2 - 0.061 X_3^2 - 0.055 X_1 * X_2$	0.997
Unevenness, %	$10.707 + 0.233 X_1 + 0.063 X_2 + 0.107 X_1^2$	0.973
Hairiness (H values)	$3.580 - 0.339 X_1 - 0.051 X_2 + 0.018 X_3 + 0.019 X_1^2$	0.996

3.2 Tenacity

Table 3 and Figure 1 illustrate the variations in yarn tenacity resulting from different processing parameters. Notably, all three parameters wield a substantial influence on the tenacity of MVS yarns, with nozzle air pressure exerting the most significant effect, followed by yarn delivery speed and card cylinder speed.

Increasing the nozzle air pressure leads to enhanced yarn tenacity. This effect can be attributed to two opposing factors: the increased tight wrappings and reduced proportion of unwrapped sections, both contribute to improved tenacity while decrease in number of core fibres reduces the tenacity. However, the dominance of the former factor results in an overall enhancement of yarn tenacity.

Conversely, higher delivery speeds result in reduced MVS yarn tenacity. This phenomenon can be explained by the role of yarn delivery speed in determining the residence time of fibers within the yarn formation zone. As the fiber bundle experiences prolonged exposure to the whirling force, it accumulates a greater amount of twist, ultimately enhancing the tenacity of MVS yarns.

Furthermore, the impact of card cylinder speed on yarn tenacity follows a nuanced pattern. Initially, increasing cylinder speed leads to higher yarn tenacity, likely due to improved fiber orientation. However, as cylinder speed continues to rise, the increase in short fiber content within the carding zone becomes a limiting factor, ultimately reducing yarn tenacity.

Figure 1: Response surface plots for the effect of process variables on yarn tenacity

3.3 Breaking Elongation

Regarding breaking elongation, our observations reveal intriguing patterns influenced by the manipulation of Process variables. An increase in nozzle air pressure initially leads to a reduction in breaking elongation due to

the presence of increased tight wrappings. However, as nozzle air pressure continues to rise, changes in the yarn structure counter intuitively cause an increase in breaking elongation. This phenomenon underscores the complex interplay between the tightening effect of increased pressure and the structural adjustments within the yarn.

At lower delivery speeds, a smaller yarn diameter is attained, primarily because the fiber bundle experiences an extended exposure to the whirling force, resulting in a higher twist imparted to the yarn. This elevated twist, accompanied by tighter regular wrappings, correlates with a reduction in breaking elongation as yarn delivery speed decreases.

In contrast, variations in card cylinder speed do not yield a significant change in elongation. This implies that altering the card cylinder speed has a relatively minimal impact on the breaking elongation of MVS yarns.

Figure 2: Response surface plots for the effect of process variables on yarn breaking elongation

3.4 Unevenness

The impact of process variables on yarn evenness and imperfections is a critical aspect of our study. Notably, nozzle air pressure plays a significant role in shaping these characteristics. As the nozzle air pressure increases, yarn evenness experiences a decline, accompanied by a noticeable increase in the number of thin places, thick places, and neps. This adverse effect can be primarily attributed to the heightened fiber loss experienced at higher pressure settings.

Similarly, when yarn delivery speed is increased, deterioration in yarn evenness was observed and an increase in the occurrence of thin and thick places. This trend highlights a clear relationship between higher delivery speeds and compromised yarn physical properties, including evenness and the presence of imperfections. Conversely, lower delivery speeds contribute to superior yarn properties, emphasizing the importance of controlling this parameter for optimal results.

Additionally, as the speed of the cylinder rises, there is a gradual increase in the U% (unevenness percentage). This increase can be attributed to fiber rupture or damage, a phenomenon that becomes more pronounced with higher cylinder speeds. This finding sheds light on the intricate dynamics between cylinder speed and yarn unevenness.

Figure 3: Response surface plots for the effect of process variables on yarn unevenness %

3.5 Hairiness

An increase in nozzle air pressure leads to a reduction in the hairiness (H values) of vortex-spun yarns. This phenomenon can be attributed to the heightened nozzle air pressure, which results in an increased whirling force

of the air stream. This, in turn, leads to more effective fiber wrapping, contributing to the decrease in yarn hairiness.

Furthermore, it has been noted that lower delivery speeds yield smaller yarn diameters. This is because the fiber bundle remains exposed to the whirling force for a longer duration, allowing for a greater amount of twist to be imparted. Consequently, the higher twist and more tightly wound regular wrappings contribute to a reduction in yarn hairiness (H values) as the yarn delivery speed decreases.

Hairiness experiences an increase as the card cylinder speed rises, primarily because of the heightened fiber rupture and the generation of short fibers within the yarn.

Figure 4: Response surface plots for the effect of process variables on yarn hairiness

4. Conclusions

This investigation underscores the substantial influence of nozzle air pressure, yarn delivery speed, and card cylinder speed on the characteristics of vortex yarns. Notably, nozzle pressure emerged as a pivotal factor profoundly affecting vortex yarn properties. Lower nozzle pressure settings yielded improvements in yarn evenness and reduced imperfections. The results unequivocally demonstrate the positive impact of increased nozzle pressure on the hairiness and tensile properties of MVS yarns, attributed to enhanced yarn wrappings.

Key findings reveal a direct relationship between delivery speed and yarn tensile properties, with an increase in delivery speed corresponding to a decline in these properties. Moreover, elevated delivery speeds contributed to heightened yarn hairiness.

In summary, this study highlights the significance of carefully selecting and optimizing delivery speed, nozzle pressure, and card cylinder speed to achieve desired properties in vortex yarns. Much like the optimization of spinning conditions in traditional ring and rotor spinning technologies, the process parameters in MVS spinning can be fine-tuned to meet specific end-use requirements. This understanding opens up avenues for enhancing the versatility and adaptability of vortex yarns in various applications.

References:

- [1] Tyagi G.K. & Sharma D., "Process-structure-property relationship of polyester-cotton MVS yarns: Part II -Influence of processing variables on yarn characteristics", *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, **29(12)**, 429–435, (2004)
- [2] Dhamija S., Varshney Rajeev Kumar and Deshdeepak," Effect of MVS process parameters on knitted fabric characteristics", *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*., **43(3)**, 330-335, (2018)
- [3] Zou Z.," Influence of the yarn formation process on the characteristics of viscose fabric made of vortex coloured spun yarns", *Fibres and Textiles in Eastern Europe*, **23 (3)**, 58-63, (2015)
- [4] Zou Z., Yu J.,Xue W., Zhu Y. & Wu J., "Analysis of the Fiber Spatial Trajectory in Vortex Spun Yarn", *Textile Research Journal*, **79**, 924–929, (2009)
- [5] Zou Z., Zheng S., Cheng L., Xi B. and Yao J.," Effect of Some Variables on the Fibre Packing Pattern in a Yarn Cross-section for Vortex Spun Yarn", *Fibers & Textiles in Eastern Europe*, **22(2)**, 40- 46, (2014)
- [6] Zou Z.Y. "Study of the Stress Relaxation Property of Vortex Spun Yarn in Comparison with Air-jet Spun Yarn and Ring Spun Yarn", *Fibers & Textiles in Eastern Europe*, **20(1)**,28-32, (2012)
- [7] Basal G. & Oxenham W., "Effects of some Process Parameters on the Structure and Properties of Vortex Spun Yarn", *Textile Research Journal*, **76**, 492–499, (2006)
- [8] Rameshkumar C., Anandkumar P., Senthilnathan P., Jeevitha R. & Anbumani N. "Comparitive Studies on Ring Rotor and Vortex Yarn Knitted Fabrics", *Autex Research Journal*.,**8(12)**,100–105, (2008)

- [9] Erdumlu N., Ozipek B., Oztuna A.S., Cetinkaya S.,” Investigation of Vortex Spun Yarn Properties in Comparison with Conventional Ring and Open-end Rotor Spun Yarns”. *Textile Research Journal*, **7(79)**, 585–595, **(2009)**
- [10] Ortlek H.G. and Onal L.,” Comparative Study on the Characteristics of Knitted Fabrics Made of Vortex-Spun Viscose Yarns”, *Fibers and Polymers*, **2(9)**, 194-199, **(2008)**
- [11] Beceren Y. & Nergis B.U., “Comparison of the Effects of Cotton Yarns Produced by New, Modified and Conventional Spinning Systems on Yarn and Knitted Fabric Performance”, *Textile Research Journal*, **78(4)**, 297–303, **(2008)**
- [12] Box G.E.P & Behnken D. W., “Some New Three Level Designs for the Study of Quantitative Variables”, *Technometrics.*, **4(2)**, 455-475, **(1960)**